

Advanced Biocomposites

High-Performance Cellulose-Based
Composites for Sustainable Materials Engineering

Outline

- Cellulose nanofibers
- Cellulose nanocomposites
- Cellulose filaments with different size scales spun of cellulose nanofiber gels
- Filament properties
- Composite properties, both experimental and estimated
- What challenges do we face in development of composites?

What are cellulose nanofibers?

- Soft wood fiber, diam 20-30 μm , length 2-5 mm
- Nanofibers, diam <100 nm, length μm -scale, can be separated from cell wall combining chemical and mechanical methods
- Mechanical properties increases with the decreased size scale
- E-modulus estimated to 140 GPa and strength 10000 MPa compared with soft wood E-modulus 12 GPa and strength 100 MPa

Why cellulose nanofibers?

- Natural resources, and can be extracted from residues
- Sustainable
- High mechanical properties
- Large surface area
- Forming gel in low concentration
- Forming strong network when dried
- Lightweight
- High thermal stability compared to many natural polymers

Cellulose nanofiber network properties

Nanofiber networks are prepared by vacuum filtration and pressing

	E-Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Strain at break (%)
Wood _{nanofiber}	11.2 ± 0.8	183 ± 14	5.0 ± 0.9
*TEMPO _{oriented}	24.6 ± 0.4	428 ± 15	2.5 ± 0.2

*Sehaqui et al ACS Appl Matr & Inter 2012

Nanocomposites by impregnation of nanofiber network

- High mechanical properties but the resin impregnation process is challenging and time consuming
- Reduce viscosity of the polymer and / or increase porosity of the network to be able to use conventional composite processing methods such as vacuum infusion
- Is it possible to align the nanofibers?

Cellulose nanofiber preforms for resin impregnation

PhD-student Tuukka Nissilä

T Nissilä et al Nanomaterials 2021, 11(2), 490; doi.org/10.3390/nano11020490

Cellulose filaments and orientation of cellulose

Ice-templating resulted in filaments with width 1 μm

Very difficult sample preparation,
low density and thin fibers, 1 μm

Cellulose filament composites by vacuum infusion

Nissilä et al Nanomaterials **2021**, 11(2), 490; doi.org/10.3390/nano11020490

Orientation of cellulose in the composite structure

Nissilä et al *Nanomaterials* 2021,11(2), 490; doi.org/10.3390/nano11020490

Composite properties

- Storage modulus increased from 2.2 to 5.4 GPa with 13 vol% cellulose filament content at room temperature
- Filaments treated with chemical surface deposition of amino silane
- Silane treated filaments resulted in better interaction with the resin as tan delta moved towards higher temperature (73 to 81 °C)

Nanomaterials 2021, 11(2), 490; doi.org/10.3390/nano11020490

Conclusions on ice-templated filaments

- Ice-templated nanocellulose filament preforms can be one way to improve the impregnation and ice-templating resulted in oriented preform structure, but it is time consuming and difficult to make large quantities
- Vacuum infusion resulted in cellulose filament content of 13 vol%
- Composites mechanical properties were increased compared to epoxy (2.5 times)
- Cellulose content was limited
- Silane treatment improved the interaction

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Spun cellulose filaments

- Spun from cellulose nanofiber /microfibril dispersion without harsh chemicals
- Continuous and lightweight
- Sustainable and bio-based
- Can we create high-performance and sustainable biocomposites of cellulose filaments?
- Develop a composite process which is leading to aligned filaments

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Motivation

Thickness $2 \mu\text{m}$
Width $80 \mu\text{m}$

- Unique micro-tape shape
- Stress transfer of microtape-shaped fiber is expected much more efficient
- Performance of microtapes in the composite is also expected to lead better properties compared to circular fibers
- Better packing is expected

Effect of shape for elastic properties

Estimated in-plane transverse modulus

Filament properties

- Average filament strength 367 MPa
- Average modulus 33 GPa
- Nanoindentation was used to measure in-plane transverse modulus, 12 GPa (needed for the micromechanical modelling)
- Challenging and time consuming to measure single filaments
- Cross section have large impact and here average cross-section was used
- Nanoindentation and the sample preparation was difficult

Ben Kahla et al Composites Part A 2025, 109153

Micromechanical modelling of filaments

- Using Halpin-Tsai model we estimated E-modulus would be around 100 GPa, if the cellulose nanofibers are completely oriented ($\eta_f = 1$)
- Experimentally measured values are lower
- Factors:
 - Orientation of the cellulose along the filament axis, and their length efficiency
 - Porosity, composition, bond between the nanofibers (G_m), Poisson's ratio
 - Need correct cross section

$$E = \eta_f \eta_o E_f \mathcal{V}_f + (1 - \mathcal{V}_f) E_m$$

$$\eta_f = 1 - \frac{\tanh(\beta l/2)}{\beta l/2}$$

$$\beta = \frac{1}{r_f} \sqrt{\frac{2G_m}{E_f \ln(R/r_f)}}$$

Orientation of cellulose nanocrystals in the filament measured with Wide Angle X-ray Spectroscopy (WAXS)

Orientation index 0.78 show that cellulose nanofibers are oriented along the microtape axis (bundle)

Unidirectional composites

Postdoc Hiba ben Kahla

- Winding of the filament roving around a metal plate
- Bio-epoxy resin (Super Sap, Entropy Resins), filament content 21-23 vol%

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Microstructure

- Longitudinal and transverse cross-sections of fracture surfaces
- Filaments are broken, no pull-outs indicating good adhesion
- Some well packed areas, which are expected to be filament bundles, also resin rich area and voids
- Need to understand why we get voids, how are these voids formed?

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Microtomography of composite structure

- Distribution of filaments is not optimal
- Need to improve packing
- Avoid twisting and void formation

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Mechanical properties

Filament content 21 vol%

Longitudinal modulus (GPa)	10
Elongation at break (%)	3
Max. strength (MPa)	120

Transverse modulus (GPa)	4.5
Elongation at break (%)	0.8
Max strength (MPa)	27

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Micromechanical modelling of mechanical properties

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Conclusions

- Promising results, so far and we believe we can improve from this initial study
- We have filaments/fibers which can be further developed for composite use
- Optimize the testing of filaments, measure correct cross-section
- Optimize the composite manufacturing process
 - Control in-plane orientation distribution of the filaments
 - Increase the filament content and decrease void content

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*Knut and Alice
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